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STYLISTIC FEATURES OF MILITARY TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND THE WAYS OF THEIR TRANSLATION

Abstract

This study is devoted to the study of the features of translation of specific military vocabulary from English into Azerbaijani. The quality and accuracy of military translation are determined, first of all, by the quality of translation of military terminology and abbreviations. The relevance of the study lies in the need to translate the continuously expanding terminological vocabulary of military vocabulary, linguistic research in which, in our opinion, is insufficiently conducted.

The main characteristic of the concept of a military term, in addition to other terminological properties, is a special sphere of functioning, which in itself, along with the definitive function and systematicity, is a feature that allows us to classify a particular word or phrase as a military term. Also, the military sphere is characterized by the widespread use of abbreviations, the diversity of their types and the high rate of renewal. In addition to extra-linguistic factors, such as the development of science and technology, the emergence of various abbreviated lexical units is explained by the "principle of least effort" or the "law of economy of speech means".

The most common methods of translating simple and complex (multi-component) terms are lexical-semantic substitutions (modulation, generalization, specification), calquing and descriptive translation. The use of descriptive translation is due not only to the different lexical-syntactic compatibility of language units, but also to the differences in the military structure of the two countries and, as a consequence, the absence of certain concepts in the Azerbaijani language.

Key words: *military term, translation, lexical unit, vocabulary, interpretation, foreign*

Military translation is a separate linguistic discipline due to high requirements for the quality and accuracy of translation, errors in which at best lead to arbitrary and subjective interpretation of the text and misunderstandings during negotiations, and at worst can cost someone's life or involve serious material costs. It requires an impeccable command not only of foreign military terminology, but also of adequate target military terminology, which is regularly replenished due to the introduction of new types of weapons, innovations in the field of materials and equipment, the emergence of new strategies and methods of combat. In addition, the translator must have deep knowledge of cultural nature, as the approach to military affairs in different countries has significant differences, which is manifested both in the structure of military statutes and in the style of presenting the material. Military translation covers all types and methods of translation, from written translation of statutes and documents to oral translation during radio exchange, not excluding two-way translation when talking on military topics, and simultaneous translation. In this work, we will consider the features of military translation on the example of the charter of the American army.

Linguistic research in the field of military translation is, in our opinion, not enough, given the speed with which the newest developments in the field of armaments appear in order to satisfy the needs of servicemen in constantly arising local conflicts, which require, in turn, all new developments and tests. These processes require constant updating of the terminological vocabulary in all languages, the necessity of translation of which determines *the relevance of this work*.

The object of the study are the features of military vocabulary on the example of the field statute of the American army, and the subject is ways of translating specific military vocabulary from English to Azerbaijani.

The main purpose of the study is to study the lexical features of the American military statute and consider ways of translating military terms and abbreviations. This goal defines the following tasks:

- 1) to consider the functional styles of the language, at the junction of which is the language of military documents, and their peculiarities at the level of vocabulary, morphology and syntax,
- 2) to study the terms and abbreviations in comparison with the general vocabulary, define the concept of "military term" and reveal its properties and spheres of functioning.
- 3) to study types of military abbreviations and abbreviations,
- 4) to study ways of translating military terms and abbreviations on the example of the field statute of the American army.

To solve the tasks set, the following *research methods* were used:

- comparative-contrastive method, which made it possible to compare observations obtained during the analysis of English and Azerbaijani military materials,
- methods of analysis and synthesis, with the help of which theoretical material on the topic under study was collected and generalized, and the results of the study were summed up,
- a method of definitional analysis, with the help of which scientific definitions of the concepts under

study were studied in order to penetrate into their content.

The practical value of the work is that the information obtained during the study allows for the appropriate expansion of the linguistic and cultural training of translators, as well as persons in one way or another connected with the armed forces and having a need for intercultural communication within the military sphere. The material presented in the work can be used in the development of practical courses on military translation, as well as in special courses and special seminars devoted to the problems of linguistic and cultural studies and intercultural communication.

Introduction

Due to its specific communicative and functional focus, military literature is at the junction of two functional styles of language – official-business and scientific-technical, the priority of one of them changes depending on the topic of a specific document – from the order of command of troops to the instructions for a radio station adopted for service. In the official-business style, unlike other styles, the genre is a powerful factor, since the genre stylistic differences of the texts of this style are expressed clearly and definitely, which allows us to single out military literature as one genre of this style. The official business style, like other functional styles, has a certain communicative purpose and, accordingly, has its own set of linguistic devices. The main purpose of business speech is to define the conditions that will ensure normal cooperation between the two parties, i.e. the purpose of business speech is to reach an agreement between two interested parties. This applies to business correspondence between representatives of different companies, and to the exchange of notes between states, and to the establishment of the rights and obligations of a soldier recorded in the military regulations of the English army, and to the procedure for meetings. All these relationships find one or another expression in the form of an official document - a letter, note, agreement, pact, law, charter, etc. Even those documents that do not clarify the terms of the agreement, but express a protest against the violation of these conditions, are associated with the main task of business speech - reaching an agreement between two or more interested persons or organizations. This main function of the style of official documents determines its features.

Military documents are replete with specialized terminology related both directly to military affairs and to various areas of technology used in the army. No norms of everyday colloquial speech, and in particular professionalisms, which often appear under the term "military slang" and which are very widely used in live communication between soldiers, are used in official documents. Thus, here too, the gap that exists between the norms of literary-written speech and everyday colloquial speech is expressed.

As I. V. Arnold notes, the most striking, but not the only, feature of this style is the use of special terminology. Each branch of science develops its own terminology in accordance with the subject and method of its work [1, p.96]. Terminology is the core of scientific

style, the last, innermost circle, the leading, most essential feature of the language of science. It can be said that the term embodies the main features of scientific style and is extremely consistent with the tasks of scientific communication.

Due to the specific communicative-functional focus, all military materials are distinguished by their richness in special military vocabulary. They widely use military and scientific-technical terminology, variable-stable and stable phrases characteristic only of the military sphere of communication, nomenclature abbreviations and symbols used only in military materials. Let us consider their features using a classic example of a military text - the US Army combat manual "SH 21-76 Ranger Handbook", published in 2000 (reissued in 2006) primarily for the needs of the US Army and to one degree or another covering all areas of military affairs. This document consists of 327 pages, of which we analyzed 3 chapters (pages 13-76) – Leadership (İdarəetmə/Komanda Mərkəzi), Operations (Əməliyyatlar) and Fire Support (Atəş dəstəyi).

The "Ranger's Manual" Charter is at the junction of two functional styles of language - official-business and scientific-technical, the priority of one of them changes depending on the topic of a particular section - from the order of command of troops to the instructions for the radio station adopted for service. The document is related to the official-business style by the wide use of impersonal and imperative sentences, clichéd constructions expressed by infinitive and participial phrases, the poverty of tense verb forms, the use of numerous parallel constructions within one sentence, the absence of tropes. From the scientific-technical style in the Charter we can observe a large number of highly specialized terms, the structured nature of the material, the presence of diagrams and illustrations. All this is associated with a certain functional load characterizing the military sphere of communication: conciseness, clarity and concreteness of formulations, accuracy and clarity of presentation, harmony of construction, clear delimitation of one thought from another, ease of perception of the transmitted information.

The subject matter of this document is very broad. "The Ranger's Manual" opens with "The Ranger's Oath", which is similar in function to the military oath of the Azerbaijani Military Charter, but is more voluminous and, the only one in the entire document, is saturated with means of artistic expression. In the "Ranger's Oath" there are epithets and emotionally charged elements of vocabulary: "*Energetically will I meet the enemies of my country*", "*elite Soldier who arrives at the cutting edge of battle*", which are practically absent from other sections of the charter. The main part of the Charter consists of 15 chapters devoted to such topics as principles of leadership and control of troops, tactical combat skills, radio regulations, rules of movement, evasion and survival, first aid. The appendix contains the "Rules of Rogers' Rangers" - a monument of military literature dated 1759, the history of the rangers, a glossary, an alphabetical index, illustrations and graphic diagrams. The chapters are clearly structured, divided into subparagraphs, within which a clear structure of construction is also maintained: most often this

is an introductory part revealing the topic of the subtitle, and instructions designed in the form of a bulleted or numbered list or table. Let us consider in turn the functional and stylistic means of the lexical level encountered in the chapters we analyzed. The charter does not include:

1) polysemantic words. Almost all words are used in one, less often in two meanings to avoid double interpretation of the text.

2) synonymous series. The language of military documents, due to its pragmatic orientation, strives to minimize the language used, accuracy and brevity, synonyms in it are redundant and, as a result, are not used in the Charter.

3) colloquial and every day vocabulary. Often used in the oral speech of the military, it is completely absent from official military documents.

4) expressive lexical elements and phraseological units. It is worth noting that in the speech of the military such elements are encountered quite often, both in oral conversation and in some types of military documents, such as: field reports, reports and transcripts of various types of negotiations, however, in field regulations ("Ranger Handbook", "Survival", "Sniper Training" and other official documents marked FM - Field manual, AR - Army regulations, ATTP - Army Tactics, Techniques and Procedures, PAM - Pamphlets, etc.) emotionally charged words and expressions are not found.

The stylistic means of the lexical level present in the chapters we have reviewed include terms (military and general scientific or general technical), the predominance of abstract vocabulary over concrete, due to the subject matter of the chapters we have reviewed (the percentage of concrete vocabulary is significantly higher in the sections devoted to radio models, weapons and ammunition), abbreviations and contractions. Thus, at the lexical level, the language of military documents belongs more to the scientific and technical functional style than to the official business style. The functional-stylistic means of the morphological level used in the text of the Charter indicate that it belongs to both the scientific and the official-business functional style: this is a low percentage of the use of concrete nouns and a high percentage of abstract (distracted) nouns, the predominant use of present tense verb forms in the meaning of "present abstract" and "present prescription", the predominance of infinitive forms over other verb forms, and the frequent use of modal verbs. In the Ranger's Manual, 100% of the sentences use verbs in the present indicative or imperative: "*The restated mission statement becomes the focus for the remainder of the estimate process*", "*Analyze terrain using OAKOC*".

The past tense is used only in the introductory chapter, "Ranger History", which is written in a journalistic style: "*The American Civil War was again the occasion for the creation of special units such as Rangers*". The future tense is found only in the "Ranger Oath", written in a fictional style: "*Readily will I display the intestinal fortitude required to fight on to the Ranger objective and complete the mission, though I be the lone survivor*".

From the point of view of syntax, in the "Ranger's Oath", which opens the statute we are studying, we observe a large number of attributive and adverbial constructions characteristic of the artistic style, complex sentences complicated by participial and adverbial phrases and inversion: "Recognizing that I volunteered as a Ranger, fully knowing the hazards of my chosen profession, I will always endeavor to uphold the prestige, honor, and high esprit de corps of the Rangers"— "Seçdiyim peşənin təhlükələrini tam bildiyim üçün bir Ranger kimi könüllü olduğumu dərk edərək, Reynçerlərin nüfuzunu, şərəfini və yüksək ruhunu qorumaq üçün həmişə çalışacağam" və ya "*Never shall I fail my comrades I will always keep myself mentally alert, physically strong, and morally straight and I will shoulder more than my share of the task whatever it may be, one hundred percent and then some*" -- *Mən öz yoldaşlarımı heç vaxt tərk etməyəcəyəm, həmişə ayıq, fiziki cəhətdən güclü və mənəvi cəhətdən möhkəm olacağam, döyüş tapşırığının nəinki öz üzərimə düşən hissəsini, harda olursa olsun, hamısını və daha çoxunu yerinə yetirəcəyəm*".

Types of terms and ways of their translation

In a general sense, military terminology includes all words and combinations denoting military concepts, i.e. concepts directly related to the armed forces, military affairs, war, etc. In addition, scientific and technical terms used in connection with military concepts (for example, track – tankın və ya hər hansı zirehli maşının tırtılı) should be classified as military vocabulary. "All other features usually attributed to terms and terminology in general: precision of meaning, unambiguity, systematicity, absence of synonymy, etc. - are nothing more than their tendency or their desirable qualities, or, finally, requirements for a "good" rationally constructed terminology. Examples of insufficient systematicity, non-rigor of the meanings of real terms, their polysemy, homonymy and synonymy are well known" [2, p.138]. Z.I. Komarova places the following requirements on a term: unambiguity, precision, brevity, systematicity, emotional-expressive neutrality, absence of modal and stylistic functions, indifference to context, conventionality, absence of synonyms and homonyms within one terminology system, etc. [3, p.92].

Military terminology may include words and combinations that, although they do not denote military concepts per se, are used almost exclusively in the military environment, and are little known or completely unknown in general use (for example, boondocks – cəngəllik; behavior report – məktub (əsgərdən) home; side arms – masa ləvazimatları), as well as some foreign borrowings, various jargons, etc., as well as emotionally charged elements of military vocabulary, which are in most cases stylistic synonyms of the corresponding military terms (for example, *doughboy* (colloquial word) and *infantryman* (term) mean "piyada")

Modern English military terminology covers the area of development of new types of weapons – primarily nuclear missile combat systems (wire-guarded missile – idarə olunan raket; rocket-assisted projectile aktiv raket mərmisi; radioactive fallout – radioaktiv tullantılar - nüvə partlayışının radioaktiv məhsulları ilə,

radioelektron və digər texniki vasitələrlə çirklənmə), electronic and other technical means (beam rider guidance – şüa istiqamətləndirilməsi; laser range finder – lazer məsafəölçən; ambush detection device – pusqu aşkar edən cihaz - (texniki) pusqu aşkar edən qurğu); terms related to the reorganization of ground forces units and higher command bodies (logistics operations center – maddi-texniki əməliyyatlar mərkəzi - arxadan idarəetmə mərkəzi); terms related to changes in certain fundamental provisions (doctrines) in tactics and operational art (electronic countermeasures – əks elektron yaxalama/ələkeçirmə).

It is necessary to keep in mind the rather significant differences in the English military vocabulary used in the USA and England. This is explained both by the specific features of the organization, armament, and

tactics of the armed forces of these countries, and by certain differences between the British and American versions of modern English.

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